

Effect of organic manure on natural occurrence of *Azolla pinnata* and its effect on rice yield

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We studied the long-term effects of organic manure and inorganic fertilizer in a rainfed rice - rice - fallow cropping system trial starting in 1972. The dry season rice crop Apr-Jul was dibble seeded; the wet season crop Aug-Nov was transplanted.

The agroclimatic zone toward the western coastal belts is characterized by sandy soil, low organic matter, with low N and K and medium P, and pH 5.3.

Jaya was the test variety. NPK was applied at 80:40:40 kg/ha. Cattle manure (CM), ammonium sulfate, super-

Data on azolla, soil pH, P, and grain yield. Kerala, India.

Treatment ^a	Fresh azolla 35 d after transplanting (t/ha)	Soil pH	Available P (kg/ha)	Mean grain yield (t/ha)		
				1989 wet season	1972-89	
					Semidry season	Wet season
CM @ 80 kg N/ha	2.1	5.45	18.8	2.8	2.1	2.3
N	—	4.73	8.4	0.1	0.8	0.6
NP	0.1	4.65	20.4	0.7	0.9	1.0
NK	—	4.68	9.4	0.9	1.1	0.7
PK	2.8	5.18	18.8	1.8	1.2	1.4
NPK	0.1	4.90	19.2	1.2	1.7	1.6
CM to supply 25% N + 75% N+PK	1.3	5.00	18.1	2.2	2.2	2.1
LSD (0.05)		0.24	6.6	0.5	—	—

^aCM = cattle manure.

phosphate, and muriate of potash were the fertilizers used (see table for treatments).

In the wet season, *Azolla pinnata* usually grows naturally for 60 d from 10-15 d after transplanting until water dries out with the cessation of the monsoon. Azolla was not seen in plots that received

no P where the soil P status was also low.

Cattle manure apparently acted as a buffer, maintaining a soil pH that favored the growth of azolla.

Azolla growth was highest in plots without applied N, maintaining moderate yield. ■

Standardization of acetylene reduction assay with field-grown aquatic legume

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To standardize a simple and efficient acetylene reduction assay for routine measurements of N₂ fixation by root- and stem-nodulating green manure leguminous plants, we determined optimum time for plant sampling, duration, and conditions for acetylene reduction assays.

Sesbania rostrata was grown in a lowland ricefield Jan-Feb 1988. Scarified seeds (40 kg/ha) were broadcast on saturated soil; the field was kept flooded starting 10 d after seeding.

The field had been transplanted to *S. rostrata* for 3 yr, but had been inoculated with *Azorhizobium caulinodans* strain IRBG46 only the first year. Plants in this experiment showed profuse spontaneous nodulation without inoculation. Measurements were taken on eight plants at 41 d after seeding.

Stem and root nodule acetylene-reducing activity (ARA) increased linearly from 0 to 2.5 h of incubation, after which it was slightly reduced

ARA of cut *S. rostrata* incubated in darkness as affected by a) incubation time, b) sampling time, c) acetylene concentration, d) time interval between field sampling and AR assay, and e) 2 consecutive days of measurements. F(A) and F(AxB) are F values from analysis of variance, due to treatment (A), and the interaction between treatment and time of incubation (AXB), both of which are significant at the 1% level. SEM = standard error of the mean.